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BONES OF BRONZE: NEW OBSERVATIONS ON THE ASTRAGALUS BONE METAL REPLICAS

BARBARA CARÈ

Riassunto. Il contributo si propone la pubblicazione di 6 manufatti inediti provenienti dal Museo della British School at Athens e dal Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum che arricchiscono il già vasto corpus delle repliche metalliche di astragali sfortunatamente prive di contesto di provenienza, tradizionalmente interpretate come pesi. Sulla base di una più ampia indagine contestuale dell'evidenza archeologica, il saggio offre un riesame di questa chiave di lettura fortemente consolidata in letteratura ed una riflessione sulle ragioni sottese alla scelta di questo motivo iconografico: l'analisi dei rinvenimenti da contesto accertato nel mondo greco permette di evidenziare il carattere prettamente votivo di tali manufatti – piuttosto che il valore funzionale – e di proporre per l'immagine dell'astragalo – ampiamente usata anche come tipo monetale – una valenza simbolica di “sostituto” dell'animale sacrificato.

Περίληψη. Το άρθρο παρουσιάζει 6 μη δημοσιευμένα μεταλλικά αντικείμενα από το μουσείο της Βρετανικής Σχολής Αθηνών και από το Μουσείο Παύλου και Αλεξάνδρας Κανελλοπούλου, τα οποία εμπλουτίζουν την ήδη πλούσια συλλογή των χάλκινων αντιγράφων αστραγάλων άγνωστης προέλευσης, που ερμηνεύονται συμβατικά ως εργαλεία μέτρησης βάρους αντί σταθμίων. Με βάση μια ευρύτερη διερεύνηση των αρχαιολογικών δεδομένων, η παρούσα εργασία προσφέρει μια επαναξιολόγηση της ερμηνευτικής προσέγγισης που έχει εδραιωθεί στην αρχαιολογική βιβλιογραφία και εξετάζει τους λόγους που οδήγησαν στην επιλογή της συγκεκριμένης εικονογραφίας: η ανάλυση των μεταλλικών αντιγράφων από τεκμηριωμένα ελληνικά αρχαιολογικά σύνολα και των χαρακτηριστικών των τελευταίων, επιτρέπουν να τονιστεί η αναθηματική – και όχι λειτουργική – αξία αυτών των αντικειμένων και να προταθεί για τον «αστράγαλο» – που έχει ευρέως χρησιμοποιηθεί ως νομισματικός τύπος.

Abstract. The paper focuses on 6 unpublished metal artefacts from the British School at Athens Museum collection and from the Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum, which enrich the already generous corpus of bronze replicas of the astragalus bone unfortunately devoid of a secure archaeological provenance, traditionally interpreted as ancient weights. Based on a broader investigation of the archaeological evidence in a context perspective, the contribution offers a reassessment of this reading consolidated in archaeological literature and reflects on the reasons behind the selection of the astragalus image for this class of materials: the analysis of the metallic replicas unearthed in Greek archaeological contexts and their depositional features allows to emphasize the votive value of these items – rather than functional – and to suggest the meaning of the astragalus shape – selected also as coin type.

1. INTRODUCTION

Six unpublished artefacts currently kept in the Museum of the British School at Athens and in the Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum¹ enrich the already wide corpus of metallic replicas of astragali² displayed in museum collections, unfortunately of unknown provenance³.

¹ I am grateful to the A' Ephorate of Prehistoric and Classical Antiquity and to the British School at Athens for granting permission to examine and publish these materials. I extend my gratitude to all the staff members of the Canellopoulos Museum and the British School at Athens, in particular to the former Assistant Director Dr. Chryssanthi Papadopoulou, for facilitating the access to the collections. This research – part of a wider project concerning the value of knucklebones in ancient ritual practices – has been carried out at the Italian Archaeological School at Athens in 2018, in the framework of the Post-Doctoral Fellowship (Corso di Perfezionamento). My sincere thanks go to the Director Prof. Emanuele Papi and to the whole staff of IASA for the help and support provided during this year; I am also indebted to my colleagues Patrizio Fileri and Yuri A. Marano for the valuable suggestions they provided and to Prof. O. Tekin for his precious advice. Of course, all shortcomings are my own. For purposes of

brevery, the different Museum collections will be referred to in an abbreviated form in the text, catalogue and figures (BM for the Museum of the British School at Athens and CM for the Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum).

² Astragalus replicas were crafted in antiquity from a variety of materials such as pottery, glass, marble, limestone; however, the practice is very well known beyond the Greek world, in different geographical contexts: among the earliest examples, for instance, are the golden astragalus from Varna, Bulgaria (LEUSCH *et alii* 2015) and the specimens made of resin, stone and ivory from the tomb of Tutankhamon (SCHAEFFER 1962, 103).

³ The two specimens stored in the Museum of the British School at Athens are part of George Finley's collection, donated in 1899; nevertheless, provenance information cannot be traced for these objects, nor for the materials kept at the Canellopoulos Museum.

Fig. 1. Susa. Bronze astragalus (riel. A. after HAUSSOULLIER 1905).

Small unmarked metallic models of this type are traditionally understood as ancient weights⁴ in analogy with monumental astragal-shaped bronze artefacts and small-scale items provided with handles, inscriptions or marks known from the Greco-Roman world⁵: the well-known giant astragalus from Susa dating to the VI century BC – based on epigraphic characters – is considered to be the earliest Greek weight of this shape (Fig. 1)⁶, while an inscription from Tegea, recording the offering of a weight of this kind by an *agoranomos* after his term in office, testifies to the existence of such artefacts in the II century AD⁷.

Astragal-shaped replicas from Classical antiquity received serious attention rather early in the long-standing debate on ancient weights and metrological systems⁸. Attention was first focused upon the mass of the large bronze astragalus kept in the National Museum at Naples and published in 1891 by Pernice, who a few years later compiled the catalogue of ancient Greek weights and pointed out the frequent occurrence of the bone as a symbol of the square lead plaques⁹. A few decades later, following the discoveries of the giant astragalus from Susa – likely originating from Didyma¹⁰ – and the bronze model from Gela, both carrying inscriptions, other scholars started devoting their attention to the epigraphic and metrological analysis of these artefacts and more generally to the investigation of the function and meaning of these offerings¹¹. In 1960, Alinei developed the topic further, speculating on the function of the natural bone as a medium of exchange in Greek pre-coinage society and its subsequent role as a weight unit (supposedly at the origin of the earliest Greek metallic unit¹²) due to it being small in scale, easily available, and always identical to

⁴ Smaller-scale replicas are also attested as having merely decorative purposes, as bezels in finger rings (ELIA-CARÈ 2004, 86, n. 87; NINOU 1978, 47, n. 84; LAFFINEUR 1980, 390-391); as beads and pendants (CURTIS 1925, 24, pl. 4, fig. 2; ÖZET 1994, 93; RUDOLF 1995, 62-64 for comparanda; KOUKOULIDOU *et alii* 2017, fig. 113); decorative bronze astragali were placed below each joint of blocks in the five-step *crepis* of the Hellenistic temple of Apollo at Claros (MORETTI *et alii* 2014, 34); D.S. V.22 refers to the mining of surface deposits of tin and the manufacture of astragal-shaped ingots in Belerion.

⁵ For a review of the known evidence, see ALINEI 1960/61, 18-19; HITZL 1996, 247-249 with previous bibliography.

⁶ Recently discussed in BRAVO 1980, 833; MANGANARO 1995, 146-148 and HITZL 1996, 151-153.

⁷ *IG* V².125, first published in BÉRARD 1893, 4-6.

⁸ In recent decades, understanding of metrology and typologies of

ancient weights, with related economic implications, has been greatly advanced: see PETRUSO 2003; ALBERTI *et alii* 2006; MICHAILIDOU 2008; IALONGO 2018 with earlier references.

⁹ PERNICE 1891; 1894.

¹⁰ PEDRIZET 1921, 64-68; PICARD 1929, 132-135.

¹¹ HAUSSOULLIER 1905, 155-165; KUBITSCHKE 1907; REHM 1958; MANGANARO 1995, 146-148.

¹² The Author postulated this connection on a linguistic basis, emphasizing the correlation between the words «talea» and «talus» – the Latin equivalent for astragalus – and the Greek *τάλαντον* (ALINEI 1961, 47-67), and in view of the affinity between the supposed value of the Homeric talent and the average weight of a bone astragalus (*Id.* 1960/61, 22; for the Homeric talent: RIDGEWAY 1887; also, SEAFORD 2004, 32, n. 65).

itself. In this perspective, he postulated a passage from the natural form to a more or less realistic metallic reproduction – in analogy with objects of certain pre-monetary value¹³ – and solicited the systematic metrological survey of the evidence for a better understanding of this class of materials¹⁴.

Ever since, the debate has been fuelled by the contribution provided by the publication of new materials¹⁵; however, the general picture regarding these artefacts is still fragmentary and many issues remain open. First, despite the fact that the importance of locating weight equipment in its contexts has become a crucial issue in metrological studies¹⁶, no attempt to put this evidence in its own archaeological context has so far been made; indeed, the research has suffered from the inadequate nature of the available documentation: publications related to these materials are mostly in the form of catalogues which do not allow context-based analysis and mass values are generally not considered. Even less attention has been paid to the reason behind the selection of the astragalus image for these items, summarily explained as a matter of artistic and artefactual tradition related to the bone's popularity as game tool¹⁷ or oracular device¹⁸. Alinei's proposal to consider this occurrence incidental to the natural bone's role as a medium of exchange has been poorly emphasized¹⁹.

The present study of the previously unpublished items in Athens has acted as a stimulus for reflecting on these points with the assistance of data related to specimens from secure archaeological contexts; although answers to the research issues involved are difficult to obtain from the archaeological record in its present state, several remarks can nevertheless be made.

2. NEW EVIDENCE FOR ASTRAGALUS METAL COPIES: TYPOLOGICAL, CHRONOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS

Three of the bronze artefacts under study (BM inv. B.088; CM inv. X436 and X1309) reproduce the natural shape of the bone (Fig. 2), while one specimen (CM inv. X449) exceptionally replicates a bone worked on its larger sides²⁰ to remove the trochlear prominences and produce regular and flat surfaces (Fig. 3). Both sets also comprise two lead replicas of worked bones (BM inv. B.89; CM inv. Δ2370); in this case, the two objects reproduce half astragali showing only the dorsal side (Fig. 4). Their dimensions range from 2.4 to 3.2 cm in height and from 1.4 to 2 cm in length, corresponding approximately to the size of natural bones.

All knucklebone replicas are solid²¹ and although evidence is insufficient to determine how they were cast, the lost-wax casting technique seems the more plausible in view of the defined contours and great details of the models²². The ornate surfaces of CM inv. X449 are likely the result of a decoration procedure, implying the inlaying of inserts into the different metal base. The item is provided, in fact, with a series of cavities in the form of apparently random dots on the bottom end and on one narrow face, and more intricate patterns on both the large faces for hosting the insert now largely missing; however, it remains unclear whether the process was not completed or the additional parts – limited traces of which are still visible on the plantar side – have been lost over time. In the absence of technical analysis, it is difficult to ascertain any significant variation in the composition of the items (and whether they are actually made of copper alloys) and whether the different patina on each is due to artificial patination procedures or corrosion.

The lack of information about the provenance of the artefacts under study makes their chronology quite controversial, spanning potentially over a wide range in view of the protracted manufacturing of

¹³ Cfr. RIDGEWAY 1892, 13-14, 317.

¹⁴ ALINEI 1960/61, 20.

¹⁵ HITZL 1996.

¹⁶ ALBERTI *et alii* 2006, 3.

¹⁷ For an overview of literary and iconographic sources, see CARÈ 2012, 403, nn. 2-4 also for earlier bibliography.

¹⁸ For the oracular practice known as "astragalomancy" – first described by PAUS. VII.25-26 – BOUCHÉ LECLERQ'S 1879 contribution is still of primary importance.

¹⁹ ALINEI 1960/61, 20. Recently Holmgren and Macaluso turned back to this point (HOLMGREN 2004; MACALUSO 2008, 31-32; also, 34ff. for a survey of finds in association with *acs rude* in votive deposits from Sicily; for such kind of hoards, also LA ROSA 1968; for a metrological analysis, ANZALONE 2009).

²⁰ The bone, situated in the hind legs of mammals, has a distinctive

cubic shape with two narrow and rounded ends and four more or less flat sides, each recognizable by its natural configuration (in animal anatomy the anterior and posterior larger sides are identified as «dorsal» and «plantar» respectively; the two lateral sides, internal and external, are designated as «lateral» and «medial»).

²¹ Astragal-shaped hollow metal replicas are also known (D'AMICIS 1984, 73: golden; a lead specimen has been recovered at the Menelaion, Sparta and I am sincerely grateful to William Cavanagh who kindly shared this information) as well as artefacts provided with a metal coating applied to the bone surface (AMANDRY 1984, 347; ΘΕΜΕΛΗΣ-ΤΟΥΡΑΤΣΟΓΛΟΥ 1997, 129; ΣΑΚΕΛΛΑΡΑΚΗΣ – ΣΑΠΟΥΝΑ-ΣΑΚΕΛΛΑΡΑΚΗ 2013, π. 86.8).

²² The less defined contours on the plantar face of BM inv. B0.88 are probably due to coarser details of the mold. All the models imitate right side bones, apart from BM inv. B088, which resembles a left astragalus.

Fig. 2. Bronze replicas of natural astragali (courtesy of the British School at Athens and the Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum; photo A.).

Fig. 3. Bronze replica of worked astragalo (courtesy of the Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum; photo A.).

Fig. 4. Lead replicas of worked astragali (Courtesy of the British School at Athens and the Paul and Alexandra Canellopoulos Museum; photo Author).

bone replicas²³. Even more questionable is the chronological setting of the metallic “worked” astragali which currently have no parallels from archaeological contexts²⁴, although they reproduce alteration techniques falling within a range of modifications well known in the ancient Mediterranean²⁵ whose functionality, however, still lacks a convincing explanation²⁶. As a matter of fact, many sites have revealed evidence for bone astragali showing abrasions of the dorsal and plantar faces, the effects of which range from a slight smoothing to an accentuated flattening so as to produce a sort of thin “plaques”²⁷. Half astragali, sectioned lengthwise and preserving only one of the large faces intact – the dorsal or the plantar

²³ Cfr. *supra*, p. 8. The discovery of a clay mould for knucklebones at Olbia is mentioned in AMANDRY 1984, 348 (see also ÖZGEN-ÖZTURK 1996, N. 213 for an IA bronze form for astragal beads. Already at the earliest recorded stages of metal working elaborate casting techniques were applied to produce metallic replicas of the bone (LEUSCH *et alii* 2015, 356 for the 5th millennium golden astragalus from Varna).

²⁴ Comparisons for the lead items (models of the dorsal side) are actually traceable on auction sites, where a generic chronology to the Byzantine period is reported; among those, a bronze specimen (replicating the plantar side) is also attested and it is included in the Pondera Online Project Database (11531), within a generic Greek chronological setting.

²⁵ Among others, GILMOUR 1997; MINNITI-PEYRONEL 2005, 12-18; CARÈ 2013, 88ff. with earlier references.

²⁶ A misleading and simplistic interpretation of the traditional sources has so far guided the interpretation of this class of archaeological evidence; the aprioristic explanation of knuckle bones as playthings and material traces of children – originated from generalized conjectures

– has become rapidly entrenched in archaeological literature (on this issue, recently CARÈ 2017). This approach has affected the investigation on bone alterations as well and different manufacturing techniques have been connected to the game practice (correlated to different roles of the gaming pieces during the game performance); nevertheless, despite the implementation of similar alterations in modern amusements involving astragali, the use of the different types of worked bones for game purposes in antiquity (as counters, tokens, etc.) is not supported by evidence (however, new observations about bones filled with lead are in KIDD 2017; for the interpretation of these artefacts as weights, see SCHAEFFER 1962, 103-105; LYNCH 2011, 161, n. 75).

²⁷ Recent experimental studies have tried to verify the functional nature of surface abrasions and loss of volume, considered as results of intense friction against a strongly abrasive body, for pottery decoration or leather working; abrasion marks on lateral and medial sides seem compatible with some of these procedures, while alterations on the larger sides are more likely intended to produce standardized objects (KOGĂLNICEANU *et alii* 2014, 293).

Fig. 5. “Half” astragali (reconstructive drawing; after CARÈ 2013).

Fig. 6. Asia Minor. Bezel ring dating to the V century BC (inv. FG 328; courtesy of the Antikensammlung, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin – Preussischer Kulturbesitz; photocredit J. Laurentius).

side (Fig. 5) – and having the opposite one smoothed²⁸ are also documented albeit rather rarely (currently almost exclusively from Greek archaeological contexts²⁹). Furthermore, imitating the shape of modified knucklebones – attributable to intentional manufacture – was not unusual in ancient metal industry³⁰.

Hence, in view of the similarity with ancient artefacts, in both shape and material³¹, the pieces examined are likely to be of considerable antiquity³², although the decoration technique of the bronze “flattened” astragal suggests a more recent chronological frame³³.

²⁸ Some bones show on their narrow faces deep linear cut marks – produced by cutting tools – clearly attributable to this kind of alteration but not completed (AMANDRY 1984, 358, fig. 17).

²⁹ *Ibid.*, 356, fig. 13; REESE 1989, 64; CARÈ 2013, 89-90, fig. 5. Similar artefacts are published in KOGĂLNICEANU *et alii* 2014, 289, fig. 6. It must be stressed in this regard – as already remarked by Amandry back in 1984 (AMANDRY 1984, 352) – that the general lack of interest for this kind of archaeological material still causes information loss or details so inaccurate as to be generally useless for this kind of investigation.

³⁰ The golden astragalus from Varna, smaller than normal pieces, resembles bones polished on the medial and dorsal faces. It also has a plantar-dorsal perforation (LEUSCH *et alii* 2015, 356); furthermore, see YOUNG 1981, 79, and BOEHMER 1972, 35, N. 15, pl. I for pierced bronze specimens from Gordion and Bogazköy respectively; GOLDMAN 1940, 418, fig. 61 for a pierced bronze model of the Classical period from Halae, Boeotia; WARDEN 1990, 65, NN. 492, 494, 496, 499 for pierced

bronze pieces from Cyrene; alterations are also replicated in pieces crafted in different materials: DEONNA 1938, 334; GUY 1938, pl. 115.24.

³¹ Lead replicas of the bone are also certainly attested in antiquity: for finds from domestic contexts, see ROBINSON 1941, 502-503, nn. 2566-2567, one inscribed); from graves, see LAURENZI 1936, 182-183; ROBINSON 1941, 2565; ARSLAN 1986, 1044; from sanctuaries, see FURTWÄNGLER 1890, 191; RAUBITSCHKE 1998, n. 398. Dodwell (1819, 519) reported the finding of some lead specimens during his travel through Greece in the early 1800.

³² Cfr. *CPAI*, Turkey 2, pl. 02, N. 095 for a similar bronze astragalus dating to the Hellenistic – Early Roman Age, whose interpretation as a weight is considered uncertain (cfr. fn. 24).

³³ The Damascene technique – sparsely attested already in the Early Bronze Age (BERGER *et alii* 2013 with previous bibliography) – was popular throughout the Byzantine period (an unworked astragalus with Damascene decoration has been traced on an auction site where it is dated to the Islamic period: 1300-1500).

Yet little can be said about the function of these copies; in the absence of verified contexts and marks of any kind to indicate their function as weighing tools, this conventional interpretation proves to be rather speculative at the current state of research³⁴. Furthermore, as for the “worked” astragali, if this explanation would still be plausible for the flattened piece, considering features such as the flat shape and the silver inlays³⁵ (yet it does not resemble any standardized weight³⁶), it is less convincing for the lead half astragali³⁷. Literary references to these items support the theory of them being artefacts with a peculiar status and significance.

In his *Symposium*, Plato introduces, through Aristophanes’ speech, the conceit of human beings as σύμβολα split in two halves, and explains amorous attraction as aiming at recovering the lost original unity by seeking the consistent and symmetric countersign³⁸. In another passage, the term σύμβολον is replaced by the apax «λίσπη»³⁹, explained in the Suda lexicon as «οἱ μέσοι διαπερισμμένοι ἀστράγαλοι καὶ ἐκτετριμμένοι»⁴⁰. More explicit about the value of these items is the testimony of the scholiast on Euripides’ Medea, who, regarding the σύμβολα refers that

«οἱ ἐπιξενούμενοι τισιν, ἀστράγαλον κατατέμνοντες, θᾶτερον μὲν αὐτοὶ κατεῖχον μέρος, θᾶτερον δὲ κατελιμπα-
νον τοῖς ὑποδέξαμενοις, ἴνα, εἰ δεῖο πάλιν αὐτοὺς ἢ τοὺς ἐκείνων ἐπιξενούσται πρὸς ἀλλήλους, ἐπαγόμενοι τὸ ἥμισυ
ἀστραγάλιον, ἀνανεοῖντο τὴν ξενίαν»⁴¹.

Therefore, we cannot exclude that the link to the social ritual of hospitality could involve also the uncommon lead replicas of these symbolic objects which, made in pairs, could have acted as proof of identity, witness to the agreements and mutual bond between the two partners (Fig. 6)⁴², as largely attested by the Roman tesserae *hospitales*⁴³.

3. MATERIALS IN CONTEXT: A CRITICAL REVIEW

While an effective engagement in weighing procedures appears consistent in different chronological periods both for astragal-shaped items of considerable dimensions (most likely serving as official standard weights and control devices to be kept in sanctuaries⁴⁴) and for small-scale marked and/or handled specimens⁴⁵ (which could have been located in sacred spaces both as functional tools or dedications⁴⁶),

³⁴ On the problematic identification of weights and the required prudential approach towards unmarked tools (indeed the majority), see the observations expressed in LANG-CROSBY 1964, 2; PETRUSO 1992, 4; RAHMSTORF 2003; ALBERTI *et alii* 2006 with previous bibliography.

³⁵ Inscriptions and denominational marks engraved and inlaid, usually with silver, appear on late Imperial and Byzantine weights (KISCH 1975, 150-154; cfr. CPAI, Turkey 3, NN. 01-03 for astragal-shaped weights with inlaid denominational marks, dating to I-III AD); plaque weights of Greek tradition circulate again from the late Imperial period (LOPREATO 1982, 75).

³⁶ As for the mass it may correspond to two *uncia* of the Medieval period (10th-14th c.), but its fabric does not have any comparisons among the known standard weights.

³⁷ Nevertheless, lead was commonly used for manufacturing weights in the Aegean since the Bronze Age, additionally as core material for weights with bronze shells, for easy adjustment of the mass, due to its availability and easy casting without requiring any sophisticated metallurgical knowledge (PETRUSO 1992, 2).

³⁸ PL. *Smp.* 191d-5.

³⁹ PL. *Smp.* 192-193a7.

⁴⁰ SUID. *ss.vv.* «λίσπη», «λίσπαι», «λίσποι».

⁴¹ E. *Med.*, 613. The σύμβολον is attested in the form of private hospitality (HOM. *Od.* 9.268; 9.369-370; HDt. VI. 81; S. *Ph.* 403ff.; *σύμα* in *Il* 6.171-77) as well as in public contexts (CIG 1193; 1837b; CIG 87). The token could also convey written texts or marks (S. *Tr.* 158; about a method for conveying secret messages through pierced knucklebones in military contexts, see AEN. *Tact.* 21-22; in CLEM.AL. II.17-18 astragali are also defined as σύμβολα in the context of mystery cults).

⁴² Luschi (2008) interpreted the depiction of the Dioskuroi kneeling and shaking their hands, with two knucklebones laying on the ground, on a bezel from Asia Minor dating to the V century BC as an allusion

to this function; nevertheless, the scene more likely alludes to the game purpose of the bones providing that the two specimens depicted, showing two different sides of the bone, do not reveal signs of such alteration and the gesture of *dexiosis* is well attested in ludic context as sign of reciprocal acknowledgement between the two opponents (cfr. DASEN 2015, 89).

⁴³ For a typological survey of different materials and shapes – probably selected because of the symbolic meaning they were embedded with, see MAGGIANI 2006; LUSCHI 2008; MESSINEO 2008 (on the Greek σύμβολα see also LANG-CROSBY 1964, 76ff.).

⁴⁴ The official value of some of these artefacts and their conformity to standard measures is confirmed by inscriptions in the Roman period: for instance, a big bronze astragalus uncovered at Nîmes can be included in the group of *pondera exacta ad Castoris* – currently the only attestation of this iconographic type – thanks to the inscription which attests its conformity to the official standard weights kept in Rome (LUCIANI-LUCCHELLI 2016, 268). Moreover, see ANDRÈ-SALVINI - DESCAMPS-LEQUIME 2005, 24 for the hypothesis that the astragalus from Didyma, once moved to Susa, served as a standard measure together with the Persian bronze weight in the shape of a lion it was close to (the authors also draw attention to a possible countermark impressed on the object at Susa). For a review of the different measures and forms of weights control, see TEKIN 2016, 29-34.

⁴⁵ See HITZL 1996 for few specimens from Olympia provided with handles or suspension loops, which may suggest that they were probably strung (cfr. WARDEN 1990, 66); furthermore, CPAI, 3.2, NN. 001-002 for Late Roman specimens with handles and marks.

⁴⁶ Inventories of treasures kept in temples in many cases provide records of the weight of gold, silver, and bronze objects; we must assume that some sanctuaries were provided with weighing equipment. About the use of dedicating astragal-shaped weights, cfr. fn. 11 (also fn. 54).

Fig. 7. Olympia. Bronze astragali (courtesy of the Archaeological Museum of Olympia. Photo A.).

this usage is not unproblematic for most of the small unmarked artefacts detected in Greek archaeological contexts⁴⁷, which first appear during the Geometric-Archaic transition (Fig. 8)⁴⁸.

Indeed, the small unmarked replicas are currently almost exclusively concentrated to votive areas, while contemporaneous evidence from settlements, which are privileged contexts hinting at a practical function⁴⁹, is very scanty⁵⁰. Moreover, the association with other weighing devices is rarely attested, nor is grouping in sets with a range of different scales⁵¹; in fact, assemblages of metal astragali – like the one from the sanctuary of Olympia, which included also objects morphologically different from the ones being studied here⁵² (Fig. 7) – are quite exceptional⁵³ since these artefacts (sometimes associated with natural bones) commonly occur as isolated pieces.

Although the exact location of astragal replicas is not always clear because of a not easily determinable stratigraphic provenance, the significant concentration in sacred places and their non-functional character suggest that they indeed had a votive value⁵⁴; on the other hand, the inscription on the monumental bronze astragal from Susa – as said one of the earlier examples of astragalus replicas – qualifies the offering as *ἀγάλματα*⁵⁵, usually understood as «pleasing and valuable gift presented to the gods»⁵⁶. It may be interesting to note that the term *ἄγαλμα* was first used for indicating «precious objects», mobile goods

⁴⁷ Looking at the characteristics, which help define balance weights summarized by Rahmstorf, astragalus replicas do not fulfil almost any of the suggested criteria. Unfortunately, most of them are published without basic information on their mass, thus this feature cannot be evaluated (Cfr. RAHMSTORF 2006, 9-10).

⁴⁸ However, the earliest evidence from the Aegean is provided by a Late Cypriote grave assemblage, which included also two bone specimens (KRUMHOLZ 1982, 278; for metal replicas in MBA contexts in Anatolia, see MINNITI-PEYRONEL 2006, 14, tab. 3).

⁴⁹ For the contexts which have typically yielded balance weights, see BOBOKHYAN 2006, 94; RAHMSTORF 2006, 9-10. On the other hand, natural bones, both unworked and worked (with different surface modifications, perforated and filled with lead) appeared in the Aegean (at first in the Peloponnese and on Cyprus) during the Late Bronze Age; the functional investigation of archaeological contexts suggested that the earliest evidence comes from central buildings, workshops, commercial spaces and burials (MINNITI-PEYRONEL 2006, 19).

⁵⁰ For later evidence from domestic contexts, see ROBINSON 1941, 503, N. 2568; cfr. fn. 31 for lead specimens.

⁵¹ It is worth noting that the bone shape is not common within the large LBA weights assemblages currently known.

⁵² «In dieser Funktion gebrauchte Astragale müssen sich jedoch eindeutig von anderen Nachbildungen der tierischen Sprunggelenke unterscheiden, wie nicht zuletzt die Beispiele in Olympia lehren» (HITZL 1996, 57).

⁵³ 12 specimens – among the earliest finds currently known (late VIII to VI century BC) – have been collected from the sanctuary of Apollo Hylates at Kourion, Cyprus (OLIVER 1996, 156).

⁵⁴ An exclusive votive value is attributed to the Olympian finds in BRAVO 1980, 833, n. 120. According to Hitzl, who points out that «astragale allzu schnell als gewichte zu interpretieren», only three specimens can be interpreted as weights (1996, 57, nn. 460-462), while the others can be understood as small dedications.

⁵⁵ The interpretation as a weight was rejected by Haussoullier in his first edition: 1905, 161 (the plural form attested is considered evidence for a second specimen).

⁵⁶ For the tradition of dedicating objects of high metal value before or in the early period of monetization in central Greece, see ARAFAT 2009, 583; LYKKE 2017, 4. The alleged pair of astragali are dedicated as a tithe *ἀπὸ λείῳ* (according to HAUSSOLIER 1905, 3): as stated by Chatraïne (1968-1980, s.v. «δέκατη») the word *dekathē* is used notably in contexts of sacrifices or fiscal matters (contra JIM 2014, 48); the interpretation of the term *λείῳ* is controversial, although, as Haussoullier already emphasized (1905, 160), it is not attested in the sense of “booty” – as now generally intended – in the VI century, while is known in the sense of “field” or agricultural produce (cfr. JIM 2014, 195 for the various proposals devoid of any apparent connection between the source of the tithe and the form of the dedication, which might allude – according to the Author – to dedicators’ success in gambling or to the element of chance in gaining a rich profit).

Fig. 8. Distribution of the astragalus bone metal replicas. Acrocorinth: REESE, forthcoming; Agios Floros: VALMIN 1938, 448; Corycian Cave: AMANDRY 1984, 348; Didyma: GREAVES 2012, 190 (also for lead models from the Archaic temple of Aphrodite at Miletos); Dodona: ΕΥΑΓΓΕΛΙΔΗΣ 1952, 294, N. 20; Halae: GOLDMAN 1940, 502; Isthmia: RAUBITSCHER 1998, 111; Kourion: WALTER - VIERNEISEL 1959, 32; OLIVER 1996, 156; Logga Messinias: ΒΕΡΣΑΚΗΣ 1916, n. 31; Perachora: PAYNE 1940, 182, pl. 80; Samos: ΚΟΡΣΚΕ 1968, N. 135; Tenos: DEMOULIN 1902, 411; Thebes: BRAUN - HAEVERNICK 1981, 113-114.

carrying economic and social value, circulating in an exclusive network of exchange (an exchange with the gods in ritual contexts) in Greek pre-coinage society⁵⁷.

This points clearly to a deeper symbolic significance of the bone shape which could explain the reason behind its selection for the votive act of dedication as well as its possible value as medium of exchange, as postulated by Alinei. The hypothesis that these metal artefacts and their presence in votive spaces could be connected to game practices has proven implausible⁵⁸; moreover, the possibility that the production of this class of materials mirrors the exceptional popularity of such pastimes is not totally convincing, considering that although astragal games gained widespread acclaim in Classical antiquity in different forms of artistic expression – leading to a great variety of astragal-shaped objects⁵⁹ – there is no evidence clearly related to game practices earlier than the V century BC in Greek artistic production, in iconographic materials⁶⁰ or in literary sources⁶¹. Similarly, there is still no evidence for any actual use of metal pieces in the divinatory rite of “astragalomancy”⁶²; furthermore, it is hard to believe that these items were generally

⁵⁷ As remarked by Luce (2011, 61), production of giant-size objects is one of several processes of defunctionalisation of offerings that renders any practical use impossible, although exchange value remains: «A system that leads to removing all use value from an object is not an insignificant fact. It directly leads to the pre-monetary system». Gernet too regarded “substitution” and the reification of ideas in precious objects as an important conceptual step towards the notion of coined money (GERNET 1981; also, LAUM 1924, 81-82; an overview of different positions within the debate on the topic is found in PARISE 1988).

⁵⁸ This proposal is advanced in KRUMHOLZ 1982, 278; WARDEN 1990, 66. The ludic purpose of metallic *astragali*, although evoked by

literary sources (A.R. III.114ff.) is more likely referred to as a symbolic value rather than a practical *astragali*.

⁵⁹ For an overview, see HAMPE 1951.

⁶⁰ Among the first iconographic evidence, almost contemporary to bone replicas, are the earliest Athenian coins, the so-called *wappenmünzen* (KROLL 1993): although the reasons for the selection of the bone shape as iconographic type has never been so far investigated.

⁶¹ The only exception is represented by the occurrence in HOM. II. XXIII.83-92.

⁶² In this sense, GREAVES 2012, 195. At the present state, the first literary evidence dates to the Roman period (SVET. Tib. 14).

Remains of the activity at the altar (on top or next to the altar):

	<i>Cronology</i>	<i>Ashes and/or other bone remains</i>	<i>Worked astragali / Replicas</i>
Sanctuary of Apollo Hylates, Kourion	late VII century BC	x	
Altar U - Kommos	700-600 BC	x	x
Sanctuary of Apollo, Didyma	Archaic period	x	x
Altar of Artemis at Ephesus		x	x
Altar 1 - Sanctuary of Vryokastro, Kythnos	Archaic - Classical period	x	

Deposits of ritual debris:

	<i>Cronology</i>	<i>Ashes and/or other bone remains</i>	<i>Worked astragali / Replicas</i>
Nichoria - Unit IV-1A	X century BC		
Temple C - Kommos (burnt remains probably deriving from Temple B, double hearts)	760-650 BC	x	
Court, Temple B - Kommos (burnt fauna probably derived from Temple B, Altar U)	760-600 BC	x	x
Court, Temple B - Kommos (burnt fauna probably derived from Altar U)	760-600 BC	x	x
Upper interior pails, Kommos (deposit of burnt fauna from Rectangular Hearth 4)	650-600 BC	x	
Temple B, Rectangular hearth 4 - Kommos	650-600 BC	x	
Building Q (room 30) - Kommos (U-shaped enclosures connected to the Sanctuary area)	760-600 BC	x	x

Leftovers from ritual dining:

	<i>Cronology</i>	<i>Ashes and/or other bone remains</i>	<i>Worked astragali / Replicas</i>
Sanctuary of Demetra Thesmophoros, Bitalemi (Sicily)	late VII - middle VI century BC	x	x
Sanctuary of Demetra Malophoros, Selinus (Sicily)	early VI - V century BC	x	x
Sanctuary of Artemis, Sane (Kalkidiki) (ritual pyres)	early Archaic period	x	-

Discarded votives:

	<i>Cronology</i>	<i>Ashes and/or other bone remains</i>	<i>Worked astragali / Replicas</i>
Adyton B - Sanctuary of Vryokastro, Kythnos (?)	VII century BC	x	x

Sacrificial remains in foundation deposits

	<i>Cronology</i>	<i>Ashes and/or other bone remains</i>	<i>Worked astragali / Replicas</i>
Artemision of Ephesus ("Earlier Basis")	VII-VI century BC	x	-
Altar Court, Samothrace	VI century BC		
Altar of Aphrodite Ourania, Athens	III quarter of V century BC	x	x

Fig. 9. Assemblages of astragali connected to sacrificial matters: indicative sample from the Geometric to the Archaic-Classical period (el. A.).

meant to evoke or perform oracular rites in the area⁶³, considering that their distribution is not limited to oracular shrines and the presence of a single metal replica does not seem to be enough to postulate an oracular cult⁶⁴.

The question arises whether the bone replica – as well as the bone itself⁶⁵ – could be envisaged as a figurative substitute, as *pars pro toto*, constituting a visual representation for the whole animal, particularly in ritual contexts, as a remnant of sacrifice⁶⁶.

A study focusing on the placing of various kinds of artefacts and tools in which the ephemeral act of sacrifice found permanent embodiment – together with the remains of the victim – has shown that most

⁶³ Cfr. MORETTI *et alii* 2014, 34 for the hypothesis that the decorative metal astragali at Claros could evoke rites of astragalomancy in the sanctuary.

⁶⁴ Cleromantic practices are attested in literary and iconographical sources earlier than Pausanias' account (n. 18), although the generic sense of the term "kleros" prevents us from inferring an early – and widespread – divinatory use of astragali which is not based on direct archaeological evidence («Oracles that make use of *astragaloï* are rare enough in Greece for Pausanias to explain the function of the one he came across in his travels»: GRAF 2005, 62).

⁶⁵ In ARIST. *H.A.* II.499.27, Aristotle offers a detailed description of the bone assimilated to a body (cfr. POPLIN 1991, 33: «L'astragale est un'idéogramme naturel des pieds fourchus»).

⁶⁶ In a foundation deposit at Samothrace, astragali – although connected by the Author to a divinatory practice (LEHMANN-SPITTLE 1964, 113) – are attributed to the animals sacrificed for the dedicatory ceremony of the rock altar sometime during the VI century BC. (Cfr. LOWREY 2014 for the interpretation of bone specimens as status items deriving their value as tokens for sacrificial donations in BA and IA Syria-Palestine).

of the bronze artefacts (utensils and vessels used in the killing or cooking of an animal⁶⁷, human and animal figurines) in Greek sacred areas from the Geometric to the Classical period, were found on or around the altar, or in ash layers, often together with animal bones, and has led to the conclusion that they served as a sort of “symbolic sacrifice”⁶⁸.

It is noteworthy that the metal copies of astragali at Didyma were found in the archaic ash altar⁶⁹, intended to hold burned bones of sacrificed animals⁷⁰, and a similar location is attributed to the bronze replicas unearthed at Kourion, at the sanctuary of Apollo *Hylates*⁷¹, where also natural bones were collected in the Archaic precinct, near the altar⁷². Interestingly, the analysis of the occurrence of bone specimens in Greek votive areas and of their depositional features reveals that, apart from limited contexts characterized by unusual patterns which may indicate a possible different value of these objects⁷³, at the present state, most of the contemporary assemblages of astragali – with a variable number of specimens – have been found near altars, hearths or in pits in association with or in proximity to other faunal materials recognized as remains of sacrifices (Fig. 9)⁷⁴, either among the remnants of the activity at the altar (involving sometimes the burning of the lower parts of legs⁷⁵) or the leftovers of sacrificial meals⁷⁶.

We should probably look at this material as evidence of prime interest for clarifying the value of these artefacts. In fact, whether the bone’s presence in sacred spaces results from the ritual process itself or from a deliberate post-ritual deposition⁷⁷ – as attested for other anatomical parts such as skins or skulls with horns⁷⁸ – it appears plausible that due to its link with sacrificial matters, the bone could have served some special significance as a token offering⁷⁹ or embodiment and durable sign⁸⁰ of this mechanism of exchange and reciprocity with the gods⁸¹. This allegorical and presumably original meaning – rather than the use

⁶⁷ Implements such as sacrificial axes, roasting spits, and various kinds of vessels used for libation or for the killing and cooking, notably tripod cauldrons.

⁶⁸ RUPP 1983; ALROTH 1988; on the value of figurines as “anathemic” offerings, also PEACOCK 2013, 00.

⁶⁹ WIEGAND 1911, 41-43: the finds («eine Anzahl von bleiernen Votivastragalen»), now lost, are among the very few specimens reported from a secure archaeological context: GREAVES 2012, 195).

⁷⁰ PAUS. V.13.11. Contra GREAVES 2012, 195 who considers that the lead astragali found together with Archaic pottery at the altar, in front of the temple, provide the only direct archaeological evidence for any kind of activity that may be connected to divination.

⁷¹ Metal and terracotta figurines were recovered on top of the altar, together with calcined bones (OLIVER 1996, 156; for the association of astragali with bronze animal figurines, see also SCHMALZ 1980).

⁷² The prevalence of bone astragali deriving from right sides in the area, consistent with the preferential selection of right hind limbs for sacrifices (DAVIES 1996, 181-182), makes it clear that they come from sacrificed animals.

⁷³ The presence of astragali in Greek sacred areas is attested within a wide chronological range, from the Geometric to the Hellenistic period; in this scenario, however, based on a contextual analysis, a variety of ritual practices or different dedicatory customs can be discerned (CARÈ, forthcoming): few contexts, at the present state, stand out for the extraordinary amounts of astragalus bones uncovered in assemblages of different classes of artefacts, devoid of other animal bones; for these groupings different explanations might also be considered.

⁷⁴ The general picture is fragmentary due to the quantity and quality of information available in archaeological literature; nevertheless, several sacred contexts reveal an association of astragali with remains of sacrificial practices dating back to the LBA (cfr. DUCOS 1971, 365).

⁷⁵ Astragali were likely to be extracted during the basic division of the animal’s body which followed the joints of the skeleton, being exposed by the cutting off of metapodials, the lower parts of legs generally missing from the sacrificial scene because left attached to the hide or discarded elsewhere (EKROTH 2007, 261). According to Sebesta (1999, 210), they were probably collected by the priest, as part of the sections generally intended as priestly perquisites; nevertheless, a wide heterogeneity in sacrificial praxis has been revealed by recent researches and the ritual burning of lower legs has been also noted, spanning from the late Bronze Age to the Hellenistic period (for instance, SHAW-SHAW 2000, 682-690; HAMLAKIS-KONSOLAKI 2004, 143-144; COSMOPOULOS-RUSCILLO 2014, 265; a ritual involving burning of these anatomical parts is mentioned in H.MERC. 124-126: «The rest, including all of the feet and all of the heads, he totally destroyed with the blast of fire»). For the high incidence of foot bones, also DES COURTILS *and alii* 1996, 817; HUBER-MÉNIEL 2013, 246-247, pl. 119.

⁷⁶ Astragali also occur in association with evidence of ritual dining and/or sacrifice within “foundation deposits” (cfr. Fig. 9). Not only ash and bones deriving from *thyisia* were preserved as still being property of the gods, but also dining debris was considered important enough to be saved in the sacred place (REESE 1989, 69; EKROTH 2017a, 43; 2017b, 48). In the various assemblages, astragali are both burned and unburned, probably because of the different processes of the anatomical part they belong to (cfr. POPLIN 1984, 392 for marks discerned as evidence for skinning process and extraction of the bone which was extremely difficult without “cooking”).

⁷⁷ The presence of worked specimens included in the same deposits reveals the intentional selection of materials not deriving directly from the sacrificial act; nevertheless, these items do not reveal a special treatment in terms of depositional features (being associated with natural astragals and other bone remains), thus, the archaeological evidence at the present is insufficient for proving undoubtedly any different interpretation.

⁷⁸ For remnants of animals or selected body parts preserved at the place of sacrifice as permanent marks of the ritual act, see BURKERT 1983, *passim* (furthermore, KOPCKE 1968, 303 for *bucrania* pierced to be probably nailed; BAMMER 1998, 35-40 for horns and pierced teeth of bears; WEBB 1977, 80 for scapulae).

⁷⁹ The presence of bone remains of exotic animal species within the sacrificial deposits, for instance, is likely to be understood as remains of symbolic offerings rather than evidence of a real sacrificial act: see EKROTH 2017a, 34; also, ROUSE 1976, 389-391 for dedications of *simulacra* of real objects; in this perspective, it is tempting to correlate the use of providing astragali with gold or silver coating (see fn. 21) with the known practice of embellishing victims’ durable parts such as skins and horns.

⁸⁰ Indeed, special categories of bones like horns were kept and displayed as memorials of sacrifices (VAN STRATEN 1995, 159; EKROTH 2017a, 22, n. 25; in H.MERC. 124-126, the victims skins Hermes spread out on a rock are said to be «still there long afterwards, a long time after these things and continually»). Regarding the metal replicas, as stated by van Straten (1995, 159), it was probably a common practice to accompany the ephemeral sacrifice of an animal with the dedication of a more durable votive offering, which in its shape or decoration contained a reference to the sacrifice (cfr. ROUSE 1976, 66 for a list of metal models which were probably meant to accompany offerings in kind, tithe or first fruits, and commemorate them).

⁸¹ It has been argued that the connection and reciprocity established between immortals and mortals through the sacrificial act and the gift of meat could have served as a manner of evoking a kind of “*xenia*-relationship” (SEAFORD 1994, 7-16; PARKER 1998, 120-121); in my view, there is an interesting parallel – perhaps more than coincidental – in the role of the astragalus bone in the sphere of human *xenia* (fn. 42).

in games or prophecy – make it likely that the astragalus bone did perform the function of token of value and this probably played a role in the transition from one form of primary wealth (animal) to another (metal)⁸².

In conclusion, long confined to the category of playthings, astragali have already given proof of their complexity, due to the wide range of actual and metaphorical values they were embedded with; this analysis confirms their role as an important source of potential information for understanding ancient phenomena in which economic, symbolic and ideological meanings are strictly correlated.

It has been argued that important conceptual preconditions for the emergence of money in the form of metal tokens developed in the context of cult practice⁸³. Opening new lines of research, this contribution points to the necessity of investigating further the process of “metallization” of the astragalus bone⁸⁴ which have originated in ritual contexts. A multi-perspective standpoint and a context-based analysis of this class of evidence – which still suffers from a simplistic and uncritical reading – would contribute in decoding its significance in the ancient past.

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CATALOGUE

- BM inv. B.088. Bronze replica of natural bone.
Dark green patina. Dimensions: length 2 cm; height 3.2; width 1.5 cm. Weight: 50 gr.
- CM inv. X436. Bronze replica of natural bone.
Mottled light green patina with a few areas worn down to a yellowish brown.
Dimensions: length 1.6 cm; height 2.6 cm; width 1.8; Weight: 25 gr.
- CM inv. X1309. Bronze replica of natural bone.
Dark green patina. Dimensions: length 1.4 cm; height 2.4 cm; width 1.4; Weight: 25 gr.
- CM inv. X449. Bronze flattened astragal
Dark green patina. Dimensions: length 2 cm; height 3.2 cm; width 1.3; Weight: 50 gr.
- BM inv. B.89. Lead replica of half astragalus.
Grey patina. Dimensions: length 1.4 cm; height 2.3; width 0.5 cm. Weight: 16 gr.
- CM inv. Δ2370. Lead replica of half astragalus.
Grey patina. Dimensions: length 1.8; height 2.7; width 0.8. Weight: 25 gr.

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- CPAI, Turkey 2 = Corpus Ponderum Antiquorum et Islamicorum, Turkey 2. Istanbul Archaeological Museums: Greek, Roman, Byzantine and Islamic Weights in the Department of Metal Objects, Istanbul 2013.*
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⁸² This value would also better account for the almost contemporaneous appearance of the bone's icon on the earliest Athenian coins of the mid-sixth century BC. (for religious dedications as symbols of value on early forms of money, cfr. PAPAPOPOULOS 2012, 281).

⁸³ PARISE 1988.

⁸⁴ «Dans les astragales, on constate de manière récurrente des manifestations [...] de métallisation, avec pour constante la recherche d'une plus forte densité. Cela rapproche cet os du cercle de la monnaie, du concept physique de monnaie, sans qu'il parvienne de façon sûre à la fonction de monnaie» (POPLIN 1991, 33).

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